

ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION REFORMS UNDER IMPLEMENTATION

BERDIBAYEVA GULSHAT SULTAMURATOVNA
Assistant teacher, Department of
“Individual wrestling and natural sciences”,
Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State
University of Physical Education and Sports

Abstract. This article discusses the reforms in our country related to environmental protection and the development of environmental literacy and ecological culture of citizens, and provides feedback on the measures taken by our government in this regard to ensure the implementation of the tasks set in the normative documents adopted by our government to conserve natural and other resources, ensure the harmony of the development of the international community with nature, form a sustainable lifestyle, and conduct comprehensive educational and propaganda work.

Keywords: humanity and nature, normative documents, human development, "nature-society-man", environmental problems, rational use of natural resources, ecological culture, natural environment, practical solutions.

In today's era of globalization, the regulation of the relationship between humanity and nature, the improvement of the ecological legal literacy of the population, and the establishment of optimal methods of environmental protection have risen to the level of state policy. In this regard, a number of Laws, Decrees, and Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers have been created by our government on the basis of international law. These regulatory documents cover issues related to the conservation of natural and other resources, ensuring the harmony of the development of the international community with nature, the formation of a sustainable lifestyle, and the conduct of comprehensive educational and propaganda work, as well as support for youth initiatives. They also play an important role in the future life of the population, especially the younger generation, in harmony with nature, rational use of natural resources, the formation of ecological awareness and ecological culture, and serve as the foundation for the political, socio-economic, and cultural development of the country.

It is known that man, as a part of nature, has always satisfied his needs from the blessings it has bestowed upon him. Today, the increase in these needs and the adoption of wastefulness are causing many problems. In this process, it is necessary to emphasize the increasing anthropogenic impact on the disruption of the balance of nature. After all, at the current stage of human development, science and technology have developed to such an extent that it is characterized by the development of nuclear energy, the chemical industry, the automation of production, the improvement of information technologies, the mastery of science and technology and other more complex areas.

Today, the task of all peoples, nations and ethnic groups is to rationally use and protect natural resources without harming the environment. In particular, "restoring the ecological culture of the Uzbek people, studying the laws of its development, preserving the increasingly polluted natural environment on a global scale, showing the role of anthropogenic factors affecting the ecological balance of the biosphere, identifying the determinants of not only the social, economic, but also the political situation in this process, and finding practical solutions, has its own historical forms and stages."

The culture formed in society within the framework of social consciousness is strengthened by social and, of course, normative-legal foundations that have their own direction and content. On the basis of these documents, a certain social culture is formed, expressing the corresponding content and essence. The issues of forming ecological culture have always been resolved by adopting normative-legal foundations regulating the relations between society and nature, based on the spirit of the era and time, human demands and needs. It is worth noting that the problem of forming ecological culture has developed together with environmental education. Consequently, thanks to ecological culture, human life acquires a new purpose, content, essence, and form.

The study and analysis of the normative-legal foundations of measures to form ecological culture, the fact that the process of forming ecological culture is

established through the influence of laws and subordinate legal documents regulating social relations, is of particular importance from a scientific point of view. It is worth noting that in our country, special attention is paid to legal consistency, a progressive social and pedagogical approach in creating a regulatory and legal framework for the formation of an ecological culture.

Along with the joys of a changing lifestyle in the framework of the development of science and technology, the depletion of many ecosystems, the expansion of environmental problems such as climate change, desertification, etc., are creating problems for humans and seriously hindering the development expected in the future. As a result, the issues of environmental protection, rational use of nature, and finding ecological solutions to environmental problems are becoming more urgent tasks and are gaining attention at the international level at the level of state policy. Therefore, special attention is being paid to environmental problems in the new stage of large-scale reforms being implemented in New Uzbekistan. In particular, the fact that many laws and regulatory legal acts related to the sector have been adopted in recent years is evidence of our opinion.

Tasks such as the implementation of the national project "Green Space" and the expansion of forest areas are set as one of the priority areas in goals 79-81 of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

Ecological culture is defined in scientific circles as a manifestation of human activity aimed at coordinating the interaction and connection of society and nature. Ecological culture is formed and develops in isolation from other processes and factors related to ecology, especially factors within the content of biology. For example, it is an effort to effectively organize ecological education, promote knowledge about the rational use of nature among the population as a whole, and increase the ecological culture of the population and protect nature.

As noted, in the creation of some regulatory and legal frameworks for the formation of ecological culture in Uzbekistan, a consistent, progressive approach can be observed. Legal and social requirements for nature protection are reflected in

our Constitution. In particular, the obligation to treat the environment with care, the emphasis on the fact that natural resources, water, flora and fauna, and other natural resources are national wealth, the need for their rational use, and the fact that they are under state protection, indicate how important the social environment and legal framework are in the formation of an ecological culture.

In the course of the studies, the generalizations and analytical opinions emphasize that, precisely in order to prevent environmental problems, the normative and legal acts of the legislation aimed at forming an ecological culture of the population make a significant contribution to maintaining the vital balance between society and nature. The legal, economic and organizational foundations of preserving natural environmental conditions and rational use of natural resources are established by the Law "On Nature Protection". It is specifically stated that its purpose is to protect ecological systems, natural complexes, guarantee the right of citizens to a favorable environment, and ensure the harmonious development of relations between man and nature. The definitions and comments on such basic concepts as the fauna and its protection, biotechnical measures for their rational use are established in the Law "On the Protection and Use of the Fauna". It is emphasized that the animal world is a national treasure, and that it should be used wisely and protected.

The Law "On the Protection and Use of the Flora", adopted in 1997 and revised in 2016, defines such concepts as a botanical collection, products of the vital activity of wild plants, flora, a set of wild plants of the juniper genus, biotechnical measures for the protection and rational use of the flora, and states that the flora of our country is a national treasure, that it must be used rationally and that it is protected by the state. As is known, forests mainly perform ecological (protection of soil, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources, sanitary and hygienic, health promotion, recreation) and socio-economic functions. It is precisely these functions that the Law "On Forests" defines as a normative legal document. The law defines the main concepts of forest, forest regeneration, forest protection, reforestation, forest users,

and forest restoration. It is worth noting that, according to the law, all forests constitute the state forest fund and consist of forests of state importance, that is, forests under the control of state forestry bodies and forests used by other agencies and legal entities. It states that forests are state property, that is, national wealth, that they must be used rationally, and that they are protected by the state.

The main objectives of the Law "On Waste" are to prevent the harmful effects of waste on the life and health of citizens, the environment, reduce waste generation and ensure its rational use in economic activities.

The state cadastre is a unified state cadastre system, which consists of a system of updated information and documents on the territorial location, legal status, quantity, quality characteristics and value of a certain type of natural, economic object or other object, and these social relations are regulated in accordance with the Law "On the State Cadastre".

Also, environmental education requires special attention in educational institutions as a component of general education. After all, the cornerstone of environmental education is environmental education. The "Concept for the Development of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan", introduced by Resolution No. 434 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 2019, defines the relevance of environmental education in terms of protecting the nature, ecosystems, and environment of our country from instability and degradation, increasing the ecological culture of the population, and the need for all segments of the population, especially young people, to contribute to these extremely serious, vital issues.

‘zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi. - O‘zbekistan Respublikasi Qonun hujjatlari to‘plami, 1.05.2023 yil.

Ё

Табиатни муҳофиза қилиш тўғрисида” 1992 йил 29 январь, ЎРҚ-754-ХII-сон /

л

абекистон Республикасининг Қонуни, 27.12.1996 йилдаги 353-И-сон.

р

27.12.1996. “Атмосфера ҳавосини муҳофаза қилиш тўғрисида”

5. “Экологик назорат тўғрисида” 2013 йил 12 ноябрь, ЎРҚ-363-сон / <https://lex.uz/acts/2304953>.

6. Yazdonov Z.Sh. O‘zbek xalq ekologik madaniyati an‘analarini tiklash va rivojlantirish tendensiyalari. Falsafa fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) dissertasiyasi avtoreferati. Samarqand – 2019.

7. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 28 yanvardagi “2022–2026 yillarga mo‘ljallangan Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot Strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi PF-60-son Farmoni.

8. **O‘zbekiston Respublikasi** Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2019 yil 27 maydagi “**Ekologik ta’limni rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida**”gi 434-son Qarori. / <https://lex.uz/docs/4354743>.